

D2. 3 – Strategy on joint research activities

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List of abbreviations

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
EEE	Electrical and electronic equipment
ERN	European Remanufacturing Network
ERA	European Research Area
LUT	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology
RG	Research group
RG1	Urban and waste mining, material recycling Research Group
RG2	Processing technologies in waste recycling Research Group
RG3	Circular manufacturing Design for recycling & remanufacturing Research Group
RG4	Sustainable energy transition – Just transition Research Group
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
UM	University of Miskolc
WEEE	Waste electrical and electronic equipment

1. Executive Summary

This report is the Deliverable 2.3 for the CiRCLETECH project. It outlines the research to be carried out within the broader topic of Sustainable Circular Economy as a vehicle to drive science excellence and capacity building in UM. As explained, joint research will be carried out by cross organizational multidisciplinary research teams.

The report outlines the strategic objectives, objectives, and dedicated outcomes. The research subtopics are described in detail in this report

The Research Strategy Action Plan is then described in detail. The identification of the RG's is outlined, research cells formed around each of the RGs and key participants are named and their work is explained in this report.

The three key actions to achieve the strategic objectives are explained:

- A1) Joint research,
- A2) Publications in university journals and other related activities,
- A3) Participation in PhD actions.

And the short- and long-term mobility plans.

The next step is to continue to deliver on the actions outlined in this report, working towards D2.4: Mid-Term research report, which is due in 6 months, in M18.

This work all moves towards the actions for increasing CE technology adsorption and innovation capacity in UM and the Northern Hungarian region.

2. Introduction

The CiRCLETECH project will raise scientific excellence of the University of Miskolc (UM) in the field of sustainable circular economy research, with the aim of forming a long-lasting Research Hub, focussed on University of Miskolc (UM) and extending across Northern Hungary. Key is the partnership with Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) in the Netherlands and Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT) in Finland. At the same time this project will also develop actions in TU Delft and LUT, thus enhancing the collaboration jointly.

This report is the Deliverable 2.3 for the project. It outlines the research to be carried out within the broader topic of Sustainable Circular Economy as a vehicle to drive science excellence and capacity building in UM. Throughout the research activity, joint research will be carried out by cross organizational multidisciplinary research teams.

The report outlines the two strategic objectives, the four objectives, and four dedicated outcomes. The following subtopics will be investigated within the scope of the project, and each are described in detail in the body of this report:

- Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling
- Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling
- Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing Design for recycling & remanufacturing
- Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

The Research Strategy Action Plan is then described in detail. Key to this was the workshop which covered three important questions, the 'where, what and how', regarding the research objectives and to define new research topics for joint articles. At the same time the research groups outlined five 'directing principles' to help manage their actions. After the identification of the RG's, research cells were formed around each of the RGs and key participants are named and their work is explained in this report.

The three key actions to achieve the strategic objectives of the CiRCLETECH are explained: A1) Joint research, A2) Publications in university journals and other related activities, A3) Participation in PhD actions. They can be considered as vertical actions, however this report also identifies a horizontal intervention, A4, which is the short- and long-term mobility.

2.1. Background

One of the primary objectives of the CiRCLETECH project is to raise scientific excellence of the University of Miskolc (UM) in the field of sustainable circular economy research, with the aim of forming a long-lasting Research Hub, across Northern Hungary. Key to achieving that objective is the collaboration with Delft

University of Technology (TU Delft) in the Netherlands and Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT) in Finland. At the same time it is important to also develop actions in TU Delft and LUT, enhancing the collaboration jointly.

The creation of an operating framework of joint research helps in setting up a solid basis of research cooperation in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy, enabling the elaboration of joint research ideas, helping the uptake of technological research results in the area. The creation of CiRCLETECH Hub, through the activities of the twinning project, provides the basis of joint research and other cooperation. The operation of a regional excellence center contributes towards creating meaningful impact on regional and national level on circular economy, not only in the three member states, but also with involvement in Horizon Europe and other EU programmes.

The creation of a joint multidisciplinary research work plan to develop pathways to address common research challenges and opportunities that the partners face, specifically: connecting technological and socio-economic research activities in the field of sustainable circular economy and boosting research excellence and management capacity of the universities. Key to this is establishing multidisciplinary, dynamic, research teams across the four defined subtopics (see table 3 below) in the field of sustainable circular economy research. This will facilitate the development of responses to the practical question of connecting technological innovation with socio-economic research to enhance the sustainable circular transition.

Teams work in interaction with each other, compiling sets of measures and solutions for practice to take up as technological innovations, with particular focus on the materials flows in industrial cycles. Joint research activity fosters long-term cooperation of the three core participating partners (UM-TUD-LUT), contributing towards further integration in the European Research Agenda.

The cooperation in joint research, coupled with capacity building, activities support the involvement of UM-TUD-LUT in European research in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy and in particular attract EU funds and talent to the UM – Northern Hungarian region, connecting it more firmly to the European Research Area (ERA).

The project will help the development of scientific excellence and research management capacities by:

- improving networking and internationalization through mobility, events, joint programmes with partners;
- improving skills and knowledge in the field of formulating research strategy, creating research ideas;
- helping to understand and engage with European Research policy and challenges;
- achieving dedication, at a strategic level, within the UM and regionally;
- creating a stable and inspiring research environment, with long term perspectives, involving the partners, but also industrial, governmental and non-profit stakeholders at regional, national and EU level. UM (along with TUD & LUT) being a member of KIC EIT Raw Materials, will also consider aspects of European Innovation Ecosystems and the European Institute of Technology.

2.2. Strategic objectives and outcomes

Current strategy aims to meet two strategic objectives (SO1 and SO3), four objectives in WP2 and having at least four dedicated outcomes. This is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Strategic objectives, WP2 objectives and expected outcomes

Strategic objectives	Objectives of WP2 - Joint exploratory research for sustainable circular economy	Expected outcomes
SO1: Strengthen the science excellence and attractiveness of UM and its research staff in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy.	O2.1: Create cross organizational multidisciplinary research teams. Define/establish a Research Hub on Sustainable Circular Economy	EO1: Improved excellence capacity and resources in Widening countries enabling to close the still apparent research and innovation gap within Europe.
SO3: Enhance research cooperation and mobility between UM and its twinning partners.	O2.2: Identify research gaps in Circular Economy related topics and conduct exploratory research as a vehicle of increasing research excellence.	EO2: Enhanced strategic networking activities between the research institutions of the Widening countries and at least two internationally leading counterparts at EU level.
	O2.3: Identify legal, policy and socio-economic barriers of adsorption of technology solutions creating a good understanding of those mechanisms for better addressing them.	EO3: Raised reputation, research profile and attractiveness of the coordinating institution from the Widening country and the research profile of its staff.
	O2.4: Demonstrate the value of open science/open innovation practices towards the local ecosystem of Northern Hungary.	EO5: Improved creativity supported by development of new approaches in R&I collaboration, increased mobility (inwards and outwards) of qualified scientists.

In the proposal a long list of KPIs were determined. During the project implementation, 13 KPIs are tightly related to WP2, which are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Relevant KPIs

	Within 3 years	Within 5 years	Within 10 years
Researchers trained	20	40	200
Research workshops held (of which international)	>10 (3)	>20 (8)	>100 (50%)
Joint publications (in peer reviewed journals)	5	15	45
Participation in Horizon Europe projects (UM)	8	15	20
Joint Research teams	4 subtopics	6 subtopics	10
Joint Horizon Europe projects, submitted proposals	4	12	20
R&D cooperation agreement with local stakeholders	5	15	60
Intellectual property registrations UM	1	5	20
Participation in MSCA, Erasmus+, other personal grants, actions of UM researchers (change to 'partner researchers')	3	9	20
Participation in national and international conferences	8	15	20
Innovative products or services	4	12	35
New research ideas by CIRCLETECH team	9	25	70
Number of international students supervised	40	120	280

2.3. Research groups' focal points

To achieve our specific objectives, the CiRCLETECH Hub is being established at UM as a renowned research center in the field of sustainable circular economy. Beyond the Twinning partners, it also aims to collaborate other leading with research institutes, circular economy-related industries, startups, and policymakers, further reinforcing itself as a trusted partner.

The Hub will promote interdisciplinary and international exchange among scholars through the CiRCLETECH exchange program, enhancing research excellence at UM. Additionally, it will facilitate collaboration with industry and policy stakeholders through the CiRCLETECH impact program. This will boost the visibility of UM and the project on a national and international scale, while also enhancing UM's reputation.

The Hub will focus on developing cross-organizational multidisciplinary research teams between UM and its Twinning partners, conducting joint research activities that integrate technological and socio-economic aspects of the sustainable circular economy transition. The involvement of local stakeholders, including industry, governance, NGOs, and citizens, will foster open innovation and generate research topics related to legal, policy, and socio-economic barriers. The Hub will also engage with policy stakeholders at municipal, regional, and national levels, amplifying the impact of UM's research activities at strategic levels.

Activities are divided into four research areas, each with a Research Group, as shown in table 3 below.

Table 3: Research Groups with topic description

Research groups	Research topic description
Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling	Secondary feedstock occurrences, recovery of high value materials with a high utilization target, cross-industrial utilizations, complete coverage: from high value to high volume feedstocks # contribution to SDG9 (Industry, innovation and infrastructure). A part of this sub theme will consider Critical Materials recycling opportunities in line with the proposed EU Critical Raw Materials Act.
Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling	Advanced separation technologies, IT, robotics, logistics solutions, big data, machine learning, digital twin, simulator development, Process automation, process analytics, digitalization # contribution to SDG9 (Industry, innovation and infrastructure) and SDG12 (Responsible consumption and production).
Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing Design for recycling & remanufacturing	New solutions and markets for remanufactured products, circular services and business models. This will explore themes such as design for reman, product characteristics, reman processes and operations, reverse logistics, partnerships and new revenues. The product design aspects will contribute to design for disassembly, contributing to design for recycling. # contribution to SDG7 (Affordable and clean energy) and SDG9 (Industry, innovation and infrastructure).
Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition	Energy democracy - universal access and social justice, Energy communities and decentralization of energy systems – renewable, sustainable and local energy, Fair pay and creation of green jobs, materials needed for low carbon tech (esp. critical materials), Sustainable society and social innovation with the households in focus. Net Zero campus and city is in scope. Contribution to reaching the 2030 targets in the Net Zero Industry Act. # contribution to SDG7 (Affordable and clean energy) and SDG11 (Sustainable cities and communities).

Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling

The resources which are contained in wastes should be recovered and utilised as much as possible because of the following issues: concern about increasing global consumption of non-renewable resources, progressive shortages of primary raw materials, reduction of space available for final disposal of wastes, the need for quantity and volume reduction of wastes generated, the need for control of environmental contamination caused by emissions from waste treatment, changing social attitudes towards waste management, etc. (Cossu and Williams 2015). According to Cossu and Williams (2015) the terminology

Landfill Mining represents the activities involved in extracting and processing wastes which have been previously stocked in particular kinds of deposits (municipal landfills, mine tailings, etc.).

Urban Mining extends landfill mining to the process of reclaiming compounds and elements from any kind of anthropogenic stocks, including buildings, infrastructure, industries, products (in and out of use), environmental media receiving anthropogenic emissions. The stocked materials may represent a significant source of resources, with concentrations of elements often comparable to or exceeding natural stocks. A definition distinguishing between “stock” and “flow” resources, either anthropogenic or natural, may be necessary. Annual stocks of materials held in geological deposits, groundwater reservoirs, household and industrial buildings, infrastructure and scrap products may not vary much over time. However, annual flows of materials may change considerably from year to year, depending upon the prevailing economic situation, fashion, technical innovations, etc. Nevertheless, from both anthropogenic stock and flow resources, secondary raw materials are produced.

Resource Recovery includes the energy that can be generated by treating and managing wastes as well as materials recycling. **Materials Recycling** aims to transform selected wastes into materials that can be used in the manufacture of new products. Packaging waste (plastics, paper, cans, glass), putrescibles, bottom ash, sewage, exhausted oils, scrap tyres, WEEE, end-of life vehicles etc., are waste flows commonly considered as falling within material recycling strategies. The recovered materials after processing (not necessarily implying an extraction process) are reintroduced in production cycles. The extraction and processing of materials during urban mining is strongly based on economic feasibility. However, in some current material recycling strategies, political and social issues may drive recycling practices, sometimes inappropriately, either by following ideologies or by excluding technical options on the basis of negative public opinions.

Therefore, the **Urban and waste mining research subtopic** focuses on the technical and scientific as well as the social awareness development of materials recovery, materials recycling and resource recovery of anthropogenic stock and flow types of resources. Research is based on the existing knowledge and experience of the partner Universities as the starting point and further seeking new applications and target material streams. Recent focus areas as starting points are the followings. The social and economic aspects of urban mining including the investigation and development of public awareness of waste management and circular economy, the growth, investment and new start-ups of the field and mapping and using of artificial intelligence for this aim. Another group of research interests is related to the material

without them, production is not possible (e.g.: indium in LCDs). More recently some important raw materials mainly come from non-European countries, for example, Rare Earth Elements (REE) from China.

The amount of electrical and electronic equipment put on the market in the EU evolved from 7.6 million tonnes in 2012 to a peak of 12.4 million tonnes in 2020 (over the period 2012-2020). The total collected WEEE increased from 3.0 to 4.7 million tonnes in the same period (EUROSTAT). The amount of WEEE is generally increasing because of the intensification of technological developments, increasing population, rapid societal and economic development (developing countries access to modern technologies), and changes in consumer habits (mobile phones, decreasing product lifetimes). On the one hand, untreated WEEE is hazardous to the environment and human health; on the other hand, WEEE is a resource which should be used.

WEEE processing faces many challenges, e.g. extremely small concentrations of valuable elements, composite materials, thin layers, covering materials, rapid changes in EEE technologies, the substitution of elements, and market price variation of elements. Collection, material recycling and energetically utilization of municipal solid waste is also a considerable task nowadays.

Our research group focuses on the following material flows, and waste flows:

- E-mobility and mobility (auto parts, sensors, electronic parts, PCBs, plastic);
- E-mobility (LiBs, parts of drive train);
- WEEE (high-tech equipment, LED, displays, PCB);
- Municipal solid wastes (processing, RDF/SRF production);

And on the following research areas:

- Processing technologies in waste recycling;
- Pre-processing and processing;
- Mechanical separation;
- Separation techniques
- Advanced separation technologies;
- Critical raw materials recovery;
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
- Waste and flue gas analysis, heat transfer;
- Logistics, mechatronics, Industry 4.0 technologies, robotics.

Contribution to SDG 9: Industry, innovation, and infrastructure and SDG 12: Responsible consumption and production

or through brokers. They also need access to components to replace worn or broken parts. Finally, the remanufactured product can be returned to use, either through a supplier, or directly to the user.

Because the supply chain creates greater opportunities for interaction with the user throughout and at the end of a product's life, remanufacturers can explore more unconventional business models. These might include focussing on the services provided rather than on physical products and promoting the residual value of products and their materials rather than writing them off.

One of the Circular Economy approaches now explicitly recognised as being of extremely high economic value is remanufacturing. This is because remanufacturing can maintain a large amount of the material, energy and labour invested in complex products and keeps them at 'as-new' quality while using a fraction of the resources needed for a new product.

In contrast, recycling preserves most of a product's materials, but still requires nearly as much of the energy, labour and time as is needed to make a new product. Of course, direct reuse would need even less resource input, so, if something is still working, we should carry on using it. But with remanufacturing, when a product fails or becomes obsolete, it may not need to be thrown away: remanufacturing can return it to 'as-new' - and even elevate it to 'state-of-the-art' - for a fraction of the price of new - typically saving 30-50% of the as-new costs.

Remanufacturing has real benefits for the environment, the economy and jobs.

There are no government statistics for remanufacturing as an industrial sector, so any figures you see are based on surveys. The research field of remanufacturing is underdeveloped when compared to manufacturing

Much of the data you will see is based on early work by Professor Walter Stahel and Dr Nabil Nasr, or on reports from the EU-sponsored Horizon 2020 project *European Remanufacturing Network* (ERN) in 2015-17. The ERN consortium included TU Delft and was led by David Peck, with other TUD colleagues. This H2020 project established the European Remanufacturing Council and David Peck sits on the steering committee.

At €30 bn, the estimate of the current EU activity level may seem large, but it's still only around 2% of equivalent manufacturing activity. Considering this, the ERN project set targets for expanding remanufacturing activity, focussing on areas with high potential such as aerospace, automotive, ICT and marine. The most ambitious 'transformation' target requires a range of concerted actions by a range of parties. The European Remanufacturing Council has set the target of growing Remanufacturing activity in EU to 100bn Euro by 2030.

The ERN project also calculated the associated saving in CO₂ emissions: since remanufacturing preserves most of the physical product, it avoids using the energy associated with material extraction, refining, melting and manufacturing. So along with the economic benefits of remanufacturing, many remanufactured products can boast environmental savings - another benefit for both remanufacturer and customer.

Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

The European Union launched the 'Fit for 55' package of policies seeking to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) by a net 55% by 2030. This is a mid-term goal toward implementing the EU's Green Deal to make Europe the first climate neutral continent by 2050. Across all countries, the policy packages envision residential energy consumption to drop, facilitated by energy efficiency improvements and higher energy costs. Social welfare, in the form of the 'Social Climate Fund', may be given to those households living in energy and mobility poverty. The EU recently responded to the energy crisis brought about by Russia's war in Ukraine with the REPowerEU, which accelerates the ambition of Fit for 55.

Measuring progress of the European Union toward the SDG7 (Affordable and clean energy), SDG11 (Sustainable cities and communities) and SDG13 (Climate action) a demonstrable perpetual weakness in energy and climate issues is being addressed. Studies show that many EU Member States were failing to improve their SDGs (with special regard to SDG7, SDG11 and SDG13) in 2019. For example, in the European Union the final energy consumption (TOE per capita) was higher in 2019 than in the prescribed 2020 targets adopted in 2012 (Eurostat 2022). However, by 2020, Covid pushed the region further behind. On the surface, the restrictions (curfews, promoting home office, etc.) supported the efforts to achieve the 2020 energy and climate goals. But the long-term trends reveal that neither the European Union, nor the CEE were on the right track to achieve SDG7, SDG11 and SDG13 in 2019 (before the pandemic hit). The slowing progress indicates the lack of political, economic, and social commitment. An unjust energy transition fails to deliver on the SDGs (and 2030 energy and climate goals) and reduces the resiliency of communities, leaving them exposed to future crises.

The Sustainable energy transition research group focuses on new policies that must be implemented. The failure to improve demonstrates the overall lack of progress in decoupling economic growth from energy consumption. The energy convergence and other inequalities (especially the energy poverty) are still unresolved policy issues. There is a strong direct and indirect relationship between residential energy consumption and human well-being that refer to higher vulnerability and lower resilience. A final goal of the policy efforts to build sustainable energy systems and improve the adaptability of (energy) communities and countries, is to enhance their resiliency during periods of crisis. Energy communities represent a new approach for energy democracy and energy justice. It also includes the fair pay and creation of green jobs supporting the just transition. Northern Hungary is one of the coal regions in transition that relies heavily on fossil fuels for energy use and greenhouse gas intensive industries too.

Beyond the energy policy research other topics are also highlighted. The research group pays particular attention to the household sector which is hit hard by the energy crisis. In 2020, the household sector (as the second-largest end-use sector after transport) was responsible for 27% of final energy consumption in the European Union (Eurostat, 2022). However, in the last decade the vast energy efficiency potential in the household sector remained largely untapped, impairing global efforts to mitigate climate change. The problem is exacerbated by the fact that the share of household primary solid biomass use in residential renewable energy consumption was 82.5% in 2020 in the European Union. CEE is stuck in a traditional biomass trap,

and this together with the energy stacking theory shed light on the slow progress of the energy transition in the household sector. Regarding household activities, heating decarbonization is the key toward reducing energy poverty and increasing resilience. Smart cities and smart energy (smart appliances, smart metering) represent a new strand of research.

Beyond the social and economic aspects, energy innovation and technological improvements are also needed. Our core areas are:

- grid scale energy storage;
- decentralized energy production and island operation;
- grid immunity and stability, energy security issues;
- computational design of electrochemical processes;
- circular carbon economy: emission, GHG storage, capturing, products from CO₂;
- design of biomass-based chemical feedstocks and chemical energy carriers using computational chemistry;
- ammonia-based chemical industry and energy economy;
- computational electrochemistry;
- alternative ways of hydrogen production:
- carbon and mineral resource assessment;
- examination of technological solutions for carbon-based hydrogen production;
- blending hydrogen into the natural gas network;
- investigate of hydrogen - natural gas and synthetic gas turbines;
- LCOE (levelized cost of energy) studies.

Hydrogen is an environmentally friendly energy carrier, only water vapour is produced during its combustion. It can also be produced from fossil fuels, biomass or water. Most of the time we meet it in the media as a renewable gas, i.e. it can be produced from water with the help of a renewable energy source; but the reality is that only a few percent of the hydrogen currently produced comes from such a source. It is basically produced from natural gas, so far this has been the most economical process. The importance of hydrogen lies in its storability, since electricity and heat can easily be produced from it, but it can also be regarded as motor fuel. It can play an important role in balancing future energy networks and reducing dependence on natural gas imports.

As long as the production of hydrogen based on renewable energies develops to real industrial proportions, it is necessary to examine the possibility of how well another energy carrier is suitable for its production economically, as well as with the protection of the environment and health in mind. Thermal gasification of carbon and hydrogen-containing fuels is considered the first key technology for the transition to a hydrogen economy. However, for gasification to play a prominent role in the transition period, capital and operating costs must be reduced, and the reliability and performance of the technologies must be improved.

Expert analyses show that hydrogen produced by coal-based gasification can be more and more competitive compared to production from natural gas. By surveying Hungarian coal plants, it is possible to examine the potential amount of hydrogen that can be based on domestic coal assets. With unburned lignite and unreleased carbon dioxide, we can aim for the carbon-neutral future planned for 2050. Given the current

3. Research Strategy Action Plan

3.1. Background for the strategy planning

In May-August 2023 all RGs had a workshop aiming to touch three important questions (where, what and how) regarding their research objectives and to define new research topics for joint articles. The workshops contributed to giving better ideas for the RG Leaders and Advisors about the participants' expectations, what can work in the predefined time period.

Hereinafter the main statements and suggestions of the participants are presented, followed by the introduction of the research cells.

Table 4: Miro board summary

<p>Q1. <i>Where? Where do you want your career to be in 3 years? Name 3 things!</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - having lots of collaborations with other researchers with diverse backgrounds, - getting more expertise in my field, - having an internationally visible research group (on computational chemistry), - having a robust circular network, - having new co-authors, - developing joint papers, - publishing in a high-impact academic journal and having higher qualified professional publications, - work on high impact and meaningful topics together with like-minded colleagues (in the fields of metallurgy / Raw Materials) for the benefit of my narrower and wider environment, - having more doctoral students under my supervision, - helping my PHD students to prepare their dissertation. - getting the PhD degree, - launching the habilitation process, - getting promotion, - securing a postdoctoral position / having a postdoctoral scholarship (perhaps in abroad), - becoming good enough educator and advancing the teaching skills, - getting more experience as project manager, - having more international high-quality co-operations, - getting new ideas for research projects to work on, - having new international projects,
<p>Q2. <i>What? What can the consortium contribute to raise your international profile and scientific excellence? What are the main points for cooperation? Name 3 points!</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - getting to know good scientists, - getting access to international networks, - facilitating networking with international researchers, - helping to connect with other researchers, - finding out the same scientific research fields with other institutes or universities - opportunities for sharing research interests and cooperation connections, possibilities, - opportunities to discuss experiences, - scientific brainstorming, - getting fresh ideas, - helping to find novel and meaningful research questions/topics, - writing Q1-Q2 journal articles, - having joint publications, - creating communication channels, - providing opportunities to meet on site and to join collaboration research, - supporting conference participation, - providing trainings for grant proposal writing, - providing common training programmes complete with other university competences, - trainings of new methodology technics, - dissemination of research results (through social media), - providing possibility for visits and staff exchanges, - promoting the high impact topics together as a joint statement show similarities in problems, - helping to build high-quality research proposals, - establishing policy negotiations between our countries,

- establishing B2B negotiations between our countries,
- benchmarking,
- providing access to international common databases.

Q3. How? Give us 3 recommendations on how to organize the joint work in the Research Group!

- visit the site,
- have a discussion on the research topics,
- establish a platform online to connect with others (LinkedIn page to increase visibility and create a sense of group spirit),
- organising live meetings, events, conferences or exchanges,
- organising thematic workshops to share knowledge on our research, or on HOW we do research,
- organizing an event where CiRCLETECH PhD students can meet,
- share knowledge on new methodologies,
- improve scientific English skills,
- expanding scientific network,
- taking part in mobility programs for acquisition professional software skills,
- creating a buddy system for PhD candidates for the different universities,
- organise a meeting to form research groups,
- organise our own conference with publications,
- brainstorming in workshops,
- trainings and "writing sessions",
- professional mentoring and HE guidance,
- joint ideation workshops coupled with Horizon Europe info sessions,
- supporting early stage post docs to get fundings,
- PhDs need publications to complete their PhD, joint working can help their work,
- all partners' cities (Miskolc, Lappeeranta and the Hague) are net zero cities – building on it,
- create CRM subgroup,
- create policy connections,
- name out ambassadors who can develop B2B and policy routes between our countries,
- use an innovation methodology to name out the biggest issues together for example:
<https://www.forth-innovation.com/>
<https://warp-innovation.com/>
- Trello board with action items,
- there must be a channel (e.g. Teams chat, Slack) where you can share your ideas and needs,
- establish clear roles and having effective communication,
- face-to-face meetings are in my opinion easiest way to build long-term co-operation,
- once we have found common and detailed topics, online workshops are also good,
- share the research topics and contacts of the group members.

According to the participants feedback the research groups intend to manage their actions regarding the following directing principles:

1. **Collaboration and Diversity:** The participants emphasized the importance of establishing numerous collaborations with researchers from diverse backgrounds. This would foster the exchange of ideas and contribute to a richer research experience.
2. **Field Expertise:** The participants aimed to enhance their expertise in their respective fields. They recognized the need to stay updated with the latest advancements and deepen their knowledge to become more proficient researchers.
3. **International Visibility:** The group desired their research group to gain international recognition. This visibility would showcase their work to a broader audience and attract valuable opportunities for collaboration and funding.
4. **Circular Network:** Participants emphasized the importance of developing a robust circular network. This entails establishing solid connections with other researchers, leading to shared resources, collaboration opportunities, and a mutually beneficial research environment.

Co-authorship and Publication: The participants sought to expand their network of co-authors, particularly by developing joint papers. Publishing in high-impact academic journals and producing higher-qualified professional publications were crucial for advancing their careers.

3.2. Research cells

After the identification, following the bottom-up approach, research cells were formed in each RGs. The section below presents them.

RG1 research cells

The social and economic aspects of urban mining including the investigation and development of public awareness of waste management and circular economy, the growth, investment and new start-ups of the field and mapping and using of artificial intelligence for this aim.

RG1/1 Social awareness cell coordinator: Szabolcs Nagy

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Laura Albareda	full/ associate professor	laura.albareda@lut.fi	LUT	Business sustainability and CSR, business collective action and value creation and commons organizing.
Minttu Laukkanen	postdoc	Minttu.Laukkanen@lut.fi	LUT	Sustainable business opportunities and new business models adoption, e.g. based on sharing economy or product-service systems, as well as enhance current value chains, e.g. through value stream analysis.
Esther van der Voet	full professor	Voet@cml.leidenuniv.nl	TUD	Methodology development: life-cycle assessment, material flow analysis, substance flow analysis, natural resource accounting, and indicator development especially within the bio-based economy and in metals and the circular economy
Szabolcs Nagy	associate prof.	nagy.szabolcs@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Behavioral analysis. Market research. Economic evaluation of intellectual and innovative activity of enterprises.

Another group of research interest is related to the material sciences, such as the applied material analytical methods (microstructure analysis) of urban mining, material and recycling technologies development from the point of view of urban mining in buildings, cars, batteries, ceramics and polymers, glass foams, municipal solid wastes, magnets and motor components, etc.

RG1/2 Material sciences research cell coordinator: Andrea Simon

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Manivannan Sethurajan	postdoc	manivannan.sethurajan@lut.fi	LUT	Biological and chemical hydrometallurgy, critical raw materials, rare earth elements, metal recovery, resource recovery and waste management.
Miia John	post-doctoral researcher	Miia.John@lut.fi	LUT	Bulk ice plate, Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer, urban wastewaters, CFD Analysis of Cooling Air Velocity, naturally frozen ice in wastewater basins.
Benjamin Sprecher	full professor	B.Sprecher@tudelft.nl	TUD	Circularity assessment methods, resources used in the energy transition and how to make that circular.
René Klein	professor	Kleijn@cml.leidenuniv.nl	TUD	Conceptualisation and design of novel building products
Emese Sebe	PhD student	emese.sebe@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Pyrolysis and gasification of Refuse Derived Fuel, Thermogravimetric Analysis.
Gábor Gyarmati	PhD student	ontgabor@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Doing research on the impurities and their removal from Al alloys, Degassing of liquid Al alloys, Investigation of Chemically Bonded Sand Cores.

Andrea Simon	associate prof.	andrea.simon@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Material testing (microstructure, physical, chemical and thermal properties, etc.), Cellular ceramics and polymeric materials, foam glass, geopolymers concrete.
Emese Mesterné Kurovics	assistant res. fellow	emese.mesterne@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Material testing (microstructure, physical, chemical and thermal properties, etc.), composite materials, glass-ceramic foams.
Alexandra Hamza	dept. engineer	alexandra.hamza@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Material testing (microstructure, physical, chemical and thermal properties, etc.), foamed cement, red mud in cement foam.

Another group of research interests is related to the sampling, mapping, discovery and extraction of potential waste and landfill mining resources including municipal solid waste landfills, mine and energetic waste and by-product deposits, tailing ponds and other urban stock and flow types of resources.

RG1/3 Landfill mining research cell coordinator: József Faitli

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Seyedmohammadreza Arefzadeh	junior researcher	Seyedmohammadreza.Arefzadeh@lut.fi	LUT	Recovery of valuable metals from urban mining waste, Solvent extraction, Bio/Hydro metallurgy, Ion exchange, Circular Economy Materials characterization
Mike Buxton	full professor	M.W.N.Buxton@tudelft.nl	TUD	Sensor based material characterisation for multiple mining applications including exploration drillcore logging, mine face mapping, pre-processing, stockpiles and waste discrimination
Yongxiang Yang	professor	Y.Yang@tudelft.nl	TUD	Iron Slag, Molten materials, Metals, Desulfurization, Blast Furnace Slags, Recovery, Rare earth elements, Blast furnaces
József Faitli	professor	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Municipal Solid Wastes, Sampling, Extended Producer Responsibility, MSW landfill survey, Development of processing technologies, Air Flow Separation, Multiphase flow, Rheology, Terminal settling velocity.
Roland Romenda	PhD student	roland.romenda@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Analysis and processing of Municipal Solid Wastes, separation techniques of particulate systems, air flow separation.
András Hegedűs	associate prof.	andras.hegedus@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	GIS, model of urban rainwater drainage, morphotectonic features, digital earth models, landslide susceptibility.

Hydro- and biometallurgical research and water and wastewater treatment applied for urban mining.

RG1/4 Hydrometallurgical research cell coordinator: Valéria Mádainé-Üveges

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Eveliina Repo	professor	Eveliina.Repo@lut.fi	LUT	Selective recovery of precious metal from multiple mixtures, Sludge Dewaterability, Acid leaching of rare earths, Sustainable composite materials.
Sami Virolainen	full/associate professor	sami.virolainen@lut.fi	LUT	Hydrometallurgical separation methods, particularly liquid-liquid extraction (solvent extraction) and ion exchange.
Manivannan Sethurajan	postdoc	manivannan.sethurajan@lut.fi	LUT	Biological and chemical hydrometallurgy, critical raw materials, rare earth elements, metal recovery, resource recovery and waste management.
Niklas Jantunen	junior researcher	Niklas.Jantunen@lut.fi	LUT	Separation of zinc and iron from sulfate leachate, recovery of arsenic from concentrated sulfuric acid.
Valéria Mádainé Üveges	lecturer	valeria.uveges@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Wastewater treatment, bioprocessing, biosolubilisation, biohydrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy.
Sándor Nagy	associate prof.	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Recycling of end of life vehicles, tyres, batteries, WEEE, Municipal solid wastes processing.

In cooperation with the Materials Recycling RG - is focused on the examination of processing techniques and technologies for producing commodity materials for the downstream manufacturing including geopolimerisation and usage of industrial residues.

RG1/5 Materials recycling research cell coordinator: Roland Romenda

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Teemu Kinnarinen	full/associate professor	Teemu.Kinnarinen@lut.fi	LUT	Geopolymer composites, ultrafine wet grinding, filtration, chemical engineering. Ultrafine grinding, filtration, permeability, water treatment.
Yongxiang Yang	professor	Y.Yang@tudelft.nl	TUD	Iron Slag, Molten materials, Metals, Desulfurization, Blast Furnace Slags, Recovery, Rare earth elements, Blast furnaces
Jelle Joustra	postdoc	J.J.Joustra@tudelft.nl	TUD	Design of products containing composite materials for a circular economy
Gábor Mucsi	professor	gabor.mucsi@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Industrial waste mining, processing of silicate bearing wastes, geopolimerisation, mechanical activation, grindability, comminution.
Roland Romenda	PhD student	roland.romenda@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Analysis and processing of Municipal Solid Wastes, separation techniques of particulate systems, air flow separation.
Sándor Nagy	associate prof.	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Recycling of end of life vehicles, tyres, batteries, WEEE, Municipal solid wastes processing.

RG2 research cells

RG2/1 Mechanical Preparation of wastes: comminution

1/1. Removal of housing or casing parts from electronic wastes.

The removal of housing is an important part of the processing. This part is usually a quite homogeneous material composition, and better to separate it at the first processing step. Some examples: Li-ion batteries, car head and tail lights and PCBs, other car electronics. UM has experiences in impact crushing, which can “open” the part, without the relevant particle size reduction of the case material. Automatized opening of case, fitted for the actual size of the e-waste could be a good solution.

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Ákos Cservenák	UM	akos.cservenak@uni-miskolc.hu
Sándor Nagy	UM	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu
József Faitli	UM	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu
Annamária Polyákné Kovács	UM	annamaria.polyakne@uni-miskolc.hu
Teemu Kinnarinen	LUT	teemu.kinnarinen@lut.fi

1/2. Recovery of the heat generated by comminution

Name	Partner	E-mail
Máté Petrik	UM	mate.petrik@uni-miskolc.hu
Sándor Nagy	UM	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu
József Faitli	UM	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu
Teemu Kinnarinen	LUT	teemu.kinnarinen@lut.fi

RG2/2 Mechanical Preparation of wastes: separation

2/1. Separation in air flow

Separation in air flow has an important role also in Li-ion battery waste processing. Design a Zig zag separator could be interesting for the research work. Processing of MSW.

Name	Partner	E-mail
Gábor Szepesi	UM	gabor.szepesi@uni-miskolc.hu
Sándor Nagy	UM	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu
József Faitli	UM	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu
Teemu Kinnarinen	LUT	teemu.kinnarinen@lut.fi
Lorenzo Botto	TUD	l.botto@tudelft.nl

2/2. Sorting by shape (camera) and automatic sorting

WEEE parts are quite various, but there are well defined types (e.g.: PCB, LED, wire, rotating elements). Camera – particle recognition and control.

Name	Partner	E-mail
Zsófia Forgács	UM	zsofia.forgacs@uni-miskolc.hu
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József Faitli	UM	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu
Teemu Kinnarinen	LUT	teemu.kinnarinen@lut.fi
Ville Lahtela	LUT	Ville.Lahtela@lut.fi

RG2/3 Preparation of composite/multilayer materials, plastics

Composite materials recycling is an actual topic nowadays. E.g.: plastic packaging materials, case material of Li-ion batteries, new type of composites, WPC.

Name	Partner	E-mail
Annamária Polyákné Kovács	UM	annamaria.polyakne@uni-miskolc.hu
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József Faitli	UM	jozsef.faitli@uni-miskolc.hu
Teemu Kinnarinen	LUT	teemu.kinnarinen@lut.fi
Ville Lahtela	LUT	Ville.Lahtela@lut.fi

RG2/4 Recovery of precious metals and CE

Focus waste streams: LCD display, vehicle electronics (various PCBs).

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Sándor Nagy	UM	sandor.nagy@uni-miskolc.hu
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Ville Lahtela	LUT	Ville.Lahtela@lut.fi
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Maria Mamelkina	LUT	Maria.Mamelkina@lut.fi
Yongxiang Yang	TUD	Y.Yang@tudelft.nl

RG2/5 Utilisation of residues in construction materials

Residues could be utilized in construction materials, e.g. as a filler or reinforcement material.

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Ville Lahtela	LUT	Ville.Lahtela@lut.fi
Daria Minashkina	LUT	Daria.Minashkina@lut.fi
Seyedmohammadreza Arefzadeh	LUT	Seyedmohammadreza.Arefzadeh@lut.fi
Jaan-Pauli KIMPIMÄKI	LUT	Jaan-Pauli.Kimpimaki@lut.fi

RG3 Circular manufacturing Design for recycling & remanufacturing research cells

RG3 cells are characterised by interdisciplinarity.

RG3/1 Circular Manufacturing

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
László Rónai	professor	laszlo.ronai@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	industrial robot, robot programming, robotics, mechatronics, force feedback, sensor, microcontroller, PLC programming, modelling, data acquisition
György Hegedűs	associate prof.	gyorgy.hegedus@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	CAD design, numerical methods, tool profile, grinding, Siemens NX, Matlab, Maple, generative design, reverse engineering, rapid prototyping
József Lénárt	lecturer	jozsef.lenart@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	industrial robot, robot programming, robotics, mechatronics, sensor, microcontroller, PLC programming, data acquisition, embedded computing, FPGA, image processing
Csaba Felhő	associate prof.	csaba.felho@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	metal cutting, simulation of metal cutting, surface roughness measurement, Computer-Aided-Manufacturing, machining, Finite Element Simulation of Metal Cutting, cutting force measurement in metal cutting, coordinate measurement technology, additive manufacturing, advanced manufacturing, precision machining technology.

István Sztankovics	lecturer	istvan.sztankovics@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	assembly, cutting force, cutting procedures, efficiency, FEM, high feed milling, machining, production planning, productivity, rotational turning,, surface roughness
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RG3/2 Design for recycling and remanufacturing

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Géza Németh	lecturer	geza.nemeth@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	epicyclic traction drive, helical torsion spring, principle of self-help, self-actuating loading, reparability, design for disassembly, elongation of life rating
Ferenc Sarka	associate prof.	ferenc.sarka@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	3D technologies, additive manufacturing, 3D laser scanning, 3D optical scanning, reverse engineering, finite element method simulations of additive manufactured parts, waste reduce of additive manufacturing, FEM model of bolted connections, testing of bolt connection with FEM,
Ágnes Takács	associate prof.	agnes.takacs@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	design methodology, conceptual design, solution finding methods, idea generating, design thinking, brainstorming, product planing, design-develop-invent, design process, elements of design
Eszter Borsodi	PhD student	borsodi.eszter@student.uni-miskolc.hu	UM	design methodology, conceptual design, solution finding methods, evaluation methods, idea generating, design thinking, product planing, design process, generative design, AI-in-design, 3D printing, circular design, sustainable materials & design
Ferenc János Szabó	associate prof.	ferenc.szabo@uni-miskolc.hu , machszzf@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	optimization of machine elements, structures and products, finite element analysis of machine elements, structures and products, trend analysis and forecasting of phenomena described by sigmoid curves, multidisciplinary optimization
Gabriella Vadászné Bognár	professor	gabriella.v.bognar@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	tribology, fluid flow, Newtonian fluids, non-Newtonian fluids, surface morphology, surface pattern formations, surface pattern models, nanofluids, hybrid nanofluid, viscosity models,
György Hegedűs	associate prof.	gyorgy.hegedus@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	CAD design, numerical methods, tool profile, grinding, Siemens NX, Matlab, Maple, generative design, reverse engineering, rapid prototyping
Katalin Voith	senior research fellow	katalin.voith@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	sustainability, sustainable energy, air pollution
Kaisa Grönman		Kaisa.Gronman@lut.fi	LUT	Life cycle assessment, environmental impacts, positive environmental impacts, footprints and handprints, sustainability, circular economy, design for environment
Natalia Vinitkaia		Natalia.Vinitkaia@lut.fi	LUT	Life Cycle Assessment, Carbon footprint, Sustainability, Circular economy, Bioeconomy, Product development, bio-based materials
Jutta Nuortila-Jokinen		jutta.nuortila-jokinen@lut.fi	LUT	Circular economy, ecodesign, polymer chemistry
Nina Boorsma	postdoc	n.e.boorsma@tudelft.nl	TUD	Design methods, circular design, design implementation, conceptual design, strategic design, early-stage design, Design for Remanufacturing, design indicators, case study research, remanufacturing entrepreneurship.

RG3/3 Logistics

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Tamás Bányai	professor	tamas.banyai@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	logistics, optimisation, in-plant supply, supply chain design, vehicle routing, Industry 4.0, just-in-sequence supply, supplier selection, sustainability of logistics processes, energy efficiency in logistics
Ákos Cservenák, PhD	assistant professor	akos.cservenak@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Logistics, mechatronics, Industry 4.0 technologies, robotics, industrial robots, mobile robots, automated material handling equipments, different simulations, vehicles, traffic systems, smart trashbins, drones
Henriett Matyi	PhD student	henriett.matyi@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	logistics, packaging, digitalization, sustainable packaging, choosing the right packaging, industry 4.0, decision support system, supply chain, simulation, packaging system,
János Juhász	PhD student	janos.juhasz1@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	supply chain, SCM, logistics, just-in-sequence, just-in-time, scheduling, supply models, manufacture, service, efficiency, economical
Laszlo Erdei	PhD student	laszlo.erdei@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	manufacturing, digital twin, digital shadow, production planning, FTS, logistics, material flow, maintenance, QM, transportation.
Veres Péter	lecturer	peter.veres@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	logistics, inner logistics, logistic optimisation, optimisational algorithms, heuristics, supply chain design, vehicle routing, location search, capacity management, clustering, circular manufacturing, manufacture servicing sustainability of logistics processes, Industry 4.0, MS-Excel

RG3/4 Materials

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
György Czel	professor	gyorgy.czel@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	biopolymers, biocomposites, heat conductive polymers, materials design, new recycling technology, materials testing, smart materials, agricultural waste, implant molding technology
Ekaterina Laakso	PhD student	ekaterina.laakso@lut.fi	LUT	Li battery research, material development, electrochemical energy storage materials

RG3/5 Business

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Csilla Margit Csiszár	professor	csilla.csiszar@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Business intelligence, business database management, consumer protection, data asset, data asset management, data governance, data security, digitalisation, digital transformation, digital tools, digital skills, GDPR, information technology
Klára Szucsné Markovics	associate prof.	klara.markovics@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	sustainable facility management, capital budgeting, investment decisions, corporate resource management, energy efficiency, cost accounting, cost reduction, activity based costing, corporate profitability, key performance indicators, social innovation
America Rocio Quinteros Condorety	assistant professor	america.quinteros.condorety@lut.fi	LUT	Sustainability, energy transitions, mining countries, lithium industry, lithium-ion-batteries, recycling, circular business models, raw materials, battery value chain, qualitative methods
Nina Boorsma	postdoc	n.e.boorsma@tudelft.nl	TUD	Remanufacturing entrepreneurship

RG4 research cells

RG4 is a strongly multidisciplinary research group. The members represent many research areas with different backgrounds. Most of them are quite strong in the technical and engineering field. The others are social scientists doing qualitative and quantitative research. According to the research expertise and qualification of the RG members four main cells are formed.

RG4/1 – Clean energy production

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Jaana Laine	lecturer	jaana.laine@lut.fi	LUT	Meanings, values and emotions connected especially to forests; institutions and natural resources; environmental history
Helga Kovács	associate professor	helga.kovacs@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	biomass combustion, alternative energy sources, waste to energy, secondary raw material from energy production systems, environmental pollution, climate change, Hazardous and valuable metals in energy production systems.
Mahshid Hasankhani	PhD researcher	M.Hasankhani@tudelft.nl	TU Delft	SLO, future clean energy systems
Miia John	post-doctoral researcher	miia.john@lut.fi	LUT	Circular Economy for materials processing, technologies for Circular Economy, energy technology, environmental engineering in energy production, green chemical technology, wastewater treatment

RG4/2 – Just transition, with special regard to energy democracy

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Matti Kojo	associate professor	matti.kojo@lut.fi	LUT	energy governance and policy, nuclear power and nuclear waste management
Hanna-Mari Husu	associate professor	hanna-mari.husu@lut.fi	LUT	energy democracy, energy communities
Tekla Szép	associate professor	regtekla@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	energy efficiency, household energy consumption, energy conversation, rebound effect, traditional biomass trap, CEE, energy poverty, just transition, energy well-being, energy policy, price regulations, index decomposition analysis, econometric analysis, regional disparities in energy use
Mohammad Jaber	PhD student	regjaber@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	Energy poverty, fuel poverty, climate change, econometric analysis, energy policies, climate change policies, energy transition, energy inequality, spatial analysis, geographic information systems, path analysis
Katalin Lipták	associate professor	katalin.liptak@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	green labour market, regional differences, energy poverty, circular economy, sustainable labour market
Ágnes Horváth	associate professor	agnes.horvath@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	corporate energy management and decarbonisation, EU-ETS, energy intensive industries, district heating, Energy market challenges, energy prices, coal phase-out, strategies for

				energy sector, profitability. Focus on corporate and industry level
Adrienn Takácsné Papp	assistant lecturer	adrienn.takacsne.papp@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	energy transition global and local level, energy management at municipal level, energy policy, decarbonisation ways at industry and municipal level, Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans, profitability, coal phase-out, just transition
Jaco Quist	assistant professor	J.N.Quist@tudelft.nl	TU Delft	energy policy, rural energy transition, energy innovation

RG4/3 – Hydrogen and energy storage

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Jouni Havukainen	associate professor	jouni.havukainen@lut.fi	LUT	environmental sustainability of energy systems, environmental performance assessment, renewable energy, PowerToX, Hydrogen economy, waste management, circular economy, biogas production systems
Marianna Vadászi	associate professor	vadaszi.marianna@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	underground hydrogen storage, hydrogen trading system, hydrogen blending into natural gas pipelines, levelized cost of hydrogen, hydrogen storage, green hydrogen production methods
István Szunyog	associate professor	szunyog.istvan@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	energy storage, hydrogen storage, carbon-dioxide storage, hydrogen production methods, hydrogen in natural gas systems, cost analysis, renewable gases, underground gas storage
Minttu Laukkanen	post-doctoral researcher	Minttu.Laukkanen@lut.fi	LUT	Business models for sustainability, sustainable value creation, circular business models, sharing business models, critical raw materials, lithium-ion batteries, sustainable supply chain management, value chains, qualitative methods
Aki Grönman	associate professor	Aki.Gronman@lut.fi	LUT	Energy storage, electrolysis, turbomachinery, renewable energy, supercritical CO ₂ , wind energy, gas turbines, steam turbines, waste heat recovery, energy transition, fluid dynamics, Power-to-X, X-to-Power
Behnam Ivatloo	professor	Behnam.ivatloo@lut.fi	LUT	Sector Couping, energy hub, renewable energy integration, multi carrier energy systems, energy storage systems, energy market

RG4/4 – Urban resilience and circularity

Name	Position	Email	Partner	Key areas
Beáta Siskáné Dr. Szilasi	associate professor	beata.siskane@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	mobility, social inequalities, social sustainability, just transition
Eeva-Lotta Apajalahti	assistant professor	eeva-lotta.apajalahti@lut.fi	LUT	sustainability transitions, innovations and organisations, social practices, path

				dependence and path break-out, cultural framing, power and resources of large energy companies and challenges of energy communities
Camilo Benitez Avila	postdoc	c.a.benitezavila@tudelft.nl	TU Delft	ethics of urban resilience, decolonizing engineering and desing, energy transition materials, transitions to post-extractivism
Zoltán Nagy	associate professor	regnzo@uni-miskolc.hu	UM	resilience, smart city, complex resilience index, social, economic, environmental resilience component, regional inequalities.
Nynke van Uffelen	PhD candidate	N.vanUffelen@tudelft.nl	TU Delft	energy ethics, energy justice, justice as recognition, energy storage
America Quinteros Condoretty	PhD student	america.quinteros.condoretty@lut.fi	LUT	lithium-ion battery industry, sustainable mobility, circular economy

The RG members agree to publish their results only in Open Access journals following the Open Science guidelines. On data management, the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) will be applied.

3.3 Key pillars – implementation actions

We determine three key actions to achieve the strategic objectives of the CiRCLETECH: A1) Joint research, A2) Publications in university journals and other related activities, A3) Participation in PhD acts. They can be considered as vertical actions, however we also identify a horizontal intervention, as A4) Short- and long-term mobility. Figure 5 presents it.

Figure 7 Logical frame for actions – The CiRCLETECH HUB

A1 – Joint research

Within the research teams, the aim is to create small (international) research cells, mainly along the social science - engineering demarcation. The cells are self-organising, with the task of selecting a common theme. The RG leader and the advisor have a key role in the organisation (facilitation), but the proactive involvement of the RG members is also essential. Cell members are responsible for organising joint meetings and sharing relevant research results (articles, studies) and experiences. On this basis, research plans and outlines are prepared.

It is proposed to write and publish small papers of around 6000 words on a pilot basis. Based on experience, the research cells can be expanded, with the aim of publishing mainly in Q1-Q2 journals that could later serve as a good basis for HorizonEurope applications. An important aspect in the selection of research topics is to ensure that they are in line with EU objectives and comply with relevant strategies and legislation (e.g. Taxonomy Regulation), which is the only way to ensure that partners can build on these to submit HorizonEurope proposals.

Actions:

- forming international mini-research teams of 3-8 people, with at least two partner universities,
- identify research topics and prepare study outlines based on these,
- writing and publishing articles, papers in international journals and conference proceedings,
- presentation of results at international conferences,
- reporting on the results achieved in different media (LinkedIn, project website, newsletter, etc.),
- organisation of thematic workshops, special sessions at least bimonthly,
- follow-up of international calls for proposals, in particular HorizonEurope,
- generation of ideas for proposals, consortium building and proposal preparation based on research results.

A2 – Publications in University Journals and other related activities

The partners provide opportunities for RG members to participate in the proofreading and editing of the journals they manage. An important objective of the University of Miskolc is to improve the quality of these journals, getting the Scopus registration and the develop the citation score. TU Delft and LUT colleagues can actively contribute to this by improving the international and multidisciplinary character of the Editorial Boards and the Reviewer Boards.

Offered journals:

GEOSCIENCES AND ENGINEERING

Website: <https://ojs.uni-miskolc.hu/index.php/geosciences/index>

ISSN 2063-6997

Regional Statistics

ISSN 2063-9538 (Print)

ISSN 2064-8243 (Online)

Website: https://www.ksh.hu/terstat_eng

Economics and Econometrics – Q2 (Scimago 2022)

Geography, Planning and Development – Q2 (Scimago 2022)

Theory, Methodology, Practice (TMP) - Review of Business and Management

ISSN 1589-3413 (Print)

ISSN 2415-9883 (Online)

Website: <https://ojs.uni-miskolc.hu/index.php/tmp/index>

Építőanyag – Journal of Silicate Based and Composite Materials

online ISSN 2064-4477

Website: <https://epitoanyag.org.hu/en/>

Actions:

- publishing research results,
- join to Editorial Boards and Reviewers Board.

A3 – Participation in PhD acts

In all cases, doctoral activities (supervision, reviews, seeking for opponents) are an important part of, and form the basis for, the research carried out in universities. Joint topic leads can help to learn about each other's research areas and can contribute to improving doctoral training and the success of doctoral students.

The partners participate as external reviewers (opponents) in PhD defenses and in the work of doctoral committees. This is not only an advantage for doctoral schools, but also allows researchers to get to know each other and find common ground for joint research.

Doctoral School in the University of Miskolc:

- Mikoviny Sámuel Doctoral School
Website: <https://mfk.uni-miskolc.hu/doktori-kepzes>
- Hantos Elemér Business and Regional Sciences Doctoral School
Website: <https://gtk.uni-miskolc.hu/doktoriiskola/about>
- Antal Kerpely Doctoral School of Materials Science and Technology
<https://www.kerpely.uni-miskolc.hu/introduction>
- István Sályi Doctoral School of Mechanical Engineering Sciences
http://geik.uni-miskolc.hu/intezetek/SALYI/brief_biography

Activities:

- joint supervision, occasional publication of topics according to the rules of the Doctoral Schools,
- preparation of external reviews,
- participation in the work of doctoral committees.

A4 – Short- and long-term mobility as horizontal actions

Short and long-term mobility is key to the success of the A1, A2 and A3 activities. It allows partners to get to know each other better, gain insights into the professional work at universities and learn about different ways of organising work. The machines and instruments available in the laboratories can complement measurements that were previously carried out in isolation.

Beyond the scientific work, personal contacts are of particular importance. Mobility can help to expand the network of contacts and build good working relationships. We plan 10-16 in and outgoing international short- and medium-term mobility (staff and students) between partner organizations during the project implementation.

4. References

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Appendix 1

MIRO board results

